

METHODS OF ACHIEVING EFFICIENCY IN ART TEACHING

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Abstract. *This article discusses the development of ways to achieve efficiency in the teaching of visual arts in general secondary schools and its use in teaching processes.*

Keywords: *general, secondary education, school, efficiency, unique, talent, effective, research, recommendations, special, psychological, pedagogical, tests.*

The subject of visual arts provides elementary knowledge and skills of artistic culture necessary for every person. Because every student, regardless of what field he will work in the future, will need to rest, relax, and restore energy spent during work. He achieves this by getting acquainted with works of art created at a high artistic level in museums, exhibitions and other places, perceiving them and enjoying them. Students will have to do a certain amount of painting in their future life.

Knowledge of drawing is necessary not only for artists, designers, architects, but also for teachers, engineers, doctors, builders, agronomists, soldiers, scientists. The schools are named after their name as general secondary education schools and have the task of providing children with general, elementary knowledge and skills in visual, practical and architectural arts, among other subjects. It should also be noted that general secondary education schools do not train artists, do not intend to work with talented children and develop them.

The times require purposeful training of students studying in general secondary schools and realization of their unique talents. As noted in the "National Personnel Training Program", students with general intellectual talent, high talents, to show and develop their natural abilities in the relevant fields of knowledge and specific directions of science, their unique talents wide opportunities are created for the realization of the dream. Along with specialists from different countries of the world, experts from our Republic are also conducting effective research in this direction. They are developing various recommendations, special psychological and pedagogical tests, and special educational programs designed for targeted training of gifted students.

One of the most urgent problems of today's education sector is to improve the social, psychological and pedagogical conditions for the development of students' abilities. Achieving the set tasks requires the creation of necessary psychological-pedagogical support and conducting socio-pedagogical experiments to study various aspects of talent.

Therefore, at present, it is necessary, first of all, to predict with sufficient accuracy the direction in which students should be engaged in the future, depending on their talent, and to create pedagogical conditions that allow them to develop their talent.

The social, political and economic changes taking place in our republic have an impact on the theory and practice of education and training. Also, the modern education system sets global tasks such as comprehensive development of human abilities, ensuring the maximum manifestation of abilities, forming a creative mature person capable of self-expression.

In order to further increase the enthusiasm of students studying in general secondary schools for fine art classes and at the same time to increase the effectiveness of fine art classes, the following series of works were carried out, firstly, general secondary Scientific-theoretical and

methodical justification of the pedagogical-psychological problem of identifying the students' abilities in relation to the science of visual arts of education schools, secondly, scientific research on the study of students' talent, analysis of advanced pedagogical experiences and generalization, thirdly, to use the didactic principles of the present time in determining the interests and abilities of visual arts in general secondary schools, giving examples of the rich heritage left to us by Uzbek folk artists. It is necessary to increase their interest in horse lessons, to develop aesthetic attitude by drawing pictures of birds and animals in landscape painting.

In short, based on theoretical approaches and the situation in practice, improvement of work with students in fine arts classes, mastering of principles, development of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms and in this regard the advanced methods used in educational institutions of developed foreign countries It would not be an exaggeration to say that the study of pedagogical theories and their wide use in the teaching process is one of the urgent pedagogical problems faced by the visual arts teacher today.

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